

Reactions of the Cobaltic Ion.

Part-IV : Kinetics of the Reaction of Cobaltic Ion with Acetic Acid and Some of Its Derivatives

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The kinetics of the reaction of cobalt (III) with acetic acid have been examined in aqueous sulphuric acid. The order of reaction for the oxidant varies with the concentrations of acetic or sulphuric acid. The average values of energy and entropy of activation are 37.00 k.cals. mole⁻¹, and 45.94 cal.°K⁻¹ mole⁻¹ respectively. The effect of substitution of amino and chloro groups in the molecule of acetic acid has been briefly studied. The rates have been found in the order : .

monochlor- > trichlor- > amino- > acetic acid.

A possible mechanism has been suggested.

Swann and Xanthakos¹ reported the oxidation of acetic acid by cobalt (III) in aqueous sulphuric acid, producing carbon dioxide and water. Sharp and White^{2,3} and also Shibata and coworker⁴, investigated the kinetics of the decomposition of cobalt (III) acetate in sulphuric acid. But, the kinetic studies of the reduction of cobalt (III) with acetic acid and its amino and chloro substituted compounds have not been carried out so far. The present work has, therefore, been undertaken to investigate the mechanism involved in these reactions.

EXPERIMENTAL

The experimental procedure is similar to that described in an earlier communication⁵. In all kinetic studies of the reduction of cobalt (III) with acetic acid, the hydrogen ions furnished by acetic acid have not been accounted for.

(I) *The Reaction of Cobalt (III) with acetic acid in aqueous sulphuric acid* : The effect of acetic acid on the rate of loss of the oxidant, in three concentrations of sulphuric acid at three temperatures, has been presented in the following table. Only the average values of the rate constants have been incorporated.

1. S. Swann and T. A. Xanthakos, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, **53**, 400.
2. J. A. Sharp and A. G. White, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 110.
3. J. A. Sharp, *ibid.*, 1957, 2030.
4. M. Shibata and M. E. Kyuno, *Nippon Kagakuzasshi*, 1958, **77**, 1434.
5. J. K. Sthapak and S. Ghosh, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.* (Communicated).

TABLE I

Co(III) initial = $1.25 \times 10^{-3} M$ K-salts of $H_2SO_4 = 0.25 N$

No.	Acetic acid concentrations (M)	Temperature	Average first order rate constants $\times 10^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$		
			Sulphuric acid concentrations		
			(5.75N)	(7.75N)	(9.75N)
1.	1.00	$25^\circ \pm 0.1$	—	4.24	5.18
2.	1.50	„	—	—	7.64
3.	2.00	„	5.76	7.02	10.27
4.	3.00	„	8.06	12.51	19.14
5.	1.00	$30^\circ \pm 0.1$	8.06	9.10	11.88
6.	1.50	„	10.34	12.69	19.41
7.	2.00	„	15.11	17.57	29.27
8.	3.00	„	23.54	30.81	56.65
9.	1.00	$35^\circ \pm 0.1$	20.75	27.06	35.47
10.	1.50	„	30.19	39.10	61.93
11.	2.00	„	39.66	58.68	84.91
12.	3.00	„	64.69	96.91	—

From the above table it is clear that the order of reaction with respect to both, cobalt (III) and acetic acid, is one. The total order of the reaction is, therefore, two. This, however, is applicable only when acetic acid concentrations are between 0.25 and 2.00 M . For higher concentrations of acetic acid ($> 2.00 M$), the order of reaction with respect to cobalt (III) remains one, but for acetic acid it is more than one.

Again, for lower concentrations of acetic acid ($< 0.125 M$) the order of reaction for cobalt (III) is two (not incorporated in the table), whereas it is only fractional for acetic acid.

Thus, order of the reaction much depends upon experimental conditions.

(II) *The Reaction of Cobalt (III) with aminoacetic acid in aqueous sulphuric acid*: A few runs have been carried out to investigate the effect of substitution of an amino group in the molecule of acetic acid. Solutions of aminoacetic acid have been prepared by weighing requisite quantities of chemically pure quality reagent.

In table II, the average values of second order rate constants (with respect to Co^{3+}) under different experimental conditions have been presented.

It may, therefore, be concluded from the table II that the order of reaction with respect to aminoacetic acid is only fractional and an increase in the concentration of sulphuric acid increases the reaction rate. Hence, the reaction is similar to that between cobalt (III) and acetic acid when its lower concentrations have been used.

(III) *The Reaction of Cobalt (III) with monochlor-acetic acid in aqueous sulphuric acid*: The kinetic studies of the oxidation of monochloroacetic acid by Co(III) in aqueous sulphuric acid mostly resemble with the studies of oxidation of glycollic acid by Co(III)⁶, excepting for the velocity of the reaction which is comparatively much faster for the latter.

TABLE II

Co(III) initial = $1.25 \times 10^{-3} M$ K-salts of $H_2SO_4 = 0.25 N$

No.	Sulphuric acid concentrations (N)	Temperature	Average second order rate constant $\times 10^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$	
			Amino-acetic acid concentrations ($1.0 \times 10^{-1} M$) ($2.0 \times 10^{-1} M$)	
1.	5.75	$35^\circ \pm 0.1$	2.43	4.34
2.	7.75	„	3.11	4.50
3.	9.75	„	3.37	4.66
4.	5.75	$40^\circ \pm 0.1$	6.80	9.46
5.	7.75	„	7.30	10.41
6.	9.75	„	7.80	11.98

The order of reaction with respect to Co(III) varies from one to two depending upon the experimental conditions. For the organic acid, the order is one. One of the products of oxidation is chlorine, which indicates the fission of C-Cl bond.

(IV) *The Reaction of Cobalt (III) with trichlor-acetic acid in aqueous sulphuric acid*: The kinetics of the oxidation of trichloroacetic acid have been studied in brief. The order of reaction with respect to the oxidant is one. The average values of the first order rate constants under different experimental conditions are presented in the following table.

TABLE III

Co(III) initial = $1.25 \times 10^{-3} M$ K-salts of $H_2SO_4 = 0.25 N$

No.	Sulphuric acid concentrations (N)	Temperature	$K_1 \text{ obs.} \times 10^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$	
			Trichloroacetic acid concentrations ($1.875 \times 10^{-1} M$) ($3.75 \times 10^{-1} M$)	
1.	5.75	$30^\circ \pm 0.1$	5.64	8.06
2.	7.75	„	7.48	9.67
3.	9.75	„	11.93	15.64
4.	5.75	$35^\circ \pm 0.1$	16.83	20.47
5.	7.75	„	18.91	22.96
6.	9.75	„	26.11	32.08

From the above table it can be concluded that the order of reaction with respect to cobalt (III) is one, whilst it is fractional (or zero) for the organic compound. Hence, the total order of the reaction may be concluded to be one. Again, an increase in the concentration of sulphuric acid increases the reaction rate.

At lower temperatures a short induction period has also been observed. One of the products of oxidation is chlorine, which indicates the rupture of C-Cl bond.

Effect of Temperature : The values of temperature coefficient and energy of activation for the reaction of cobalt (III) and acetic acid in aqueous sulphuric acid are presented in the table given below :

TABLE IV

No.	Acetic acid concentrations (<i>M</i>)	Sulphuric acid concentrations		
		7.75 <i>N</i> 35-25°	7.75 <i>N</i> 35-25°	9.75 <i>N</i> 35-25°
1.	1.00	—	4.93*	6.84
2.	1.50	—	—	8.10
3.	2.00	7.00	8.35	8.26
4.	3.00	8.07	7.75	—

Energy of activation 36800 cal. 38050 cal. 35600 cal.

* (not included for calculation).

Thus, the average values of temperature-coefficient and energy of activation are 7.75 and 37.00 k.cals.mole⁻¹, respectively. The average values of the energies of activation for monochlor-, trichlor-, and amino-acetic acids are 34.30 k.cals.mole⁻¹, 30.65 k.cals.mole⁻¹, and 34.20 k.cals.mole⁻¹, respectively.

The values of frequency factors (*A*), have been calculated from an average value of the energy of activation. These, alongwith the values of entropy of activation, have been incorporated in the following table :

TABLE V

Acetic acid concentrations (<i>M</i>)	<i>A</i> × 10 ²² litres mole ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹			Entropy of activation cal °k ⁻¹ mole ⁻¹
	25°	30°	35°	
1.00	11.39	9.47	10.03	+45.81
1.50	11.20	10.32	11.69	+45.94
2.00	11.28	11.68	12.00	+46.06

Thus, the average values of frequency factor and entropy of activation are 11.01 × 10²² litres mole⁻¹ sec⁻¹, and +45.94 cal°k⁻¹mol⁻¹, respectively.

DISCUSSION

In the present study, cobalt (III) sulphate has been obtained *in situ* by the interaction of potassium cobalt (III) carbonate and sulphuric acid. The minimum concentration of sulphuric acid has been kept at 5.75 *N*, in presence of which there is hardly any reduction of cobalt (III) with water. Hence, the loss of oxidant can only be accounted for by either the catalytic influence of acetic acid on the reduction of cobalt (III) with water or by the oxidation of acetic acid.

At lower acetic acid concentrations, the reaction has been found to be of second order with respect to cobalt (III) but it is fractional for acetic acid. It is also known that in the preparation of peracetic acid, cobalt (III) acts as a catalyst. Therefore, in order to explain the observed facts one is led to conclude the following mechanism :

where the formation of dimeric cobalt (III), i.e., step (2) seems to be rate determining. The accelerating effect of hydrogen ions on the velocity of the reaction can partially be explained by step (1), and the steps (2) and (3) appear to be significant for the catalytic activity of cobalt (III) in the formation of peracetic acid. Sharp (*loc. cit.*) has also failed to explain the dependence of the second order rate constants on the initial concentrations of cobalt (III) acetate. It is also possible, however, that when higher concentrations of cobalt (III) are used, the dimeric form is converted into trimeric^{2,8} as noted below :

which is not impossible because of the nature of cobalt (III). Hence, larger concentrations of cobalt (III) leading to the formation of trimer will act as a damper on the rate of loss of cobalt (III) with acetic acid. In other words, where cobalt (III) concentrations are large, the rate constants may become an inverse function of cobalt (III) concentrations. Further work is in progress to elucidate and substantiate this presumption.

It is now necessary to discuss the variation in the order of the two reactants, *viz.*, cobalt (III) and acetic acid, as the concentration of the latter is increased. It may be opined here that at higher concentrations of acetic acid (0.125 to 2.00 *M*), the undissociated molecules of the reducing substrate are associated with cobalt (III) to yield coordinated compound, which disproportionates into cobalt (II) and an acetate free radical :

The acetate free radical will subsequently be oxidized to carbon dioxide and water. It may even be assumed that cobalt (III) sulphate directly reacts with undissociated acetic acid to yield the oxidation products. In such circumstances, the reaction will be of the first order for both cobalt (III) and acetic acid. Sharp (*loc. cit.*) has, however, failed in finding out any such relationship because very low concentration of acetic acid (0.0033 *M*) could be obtained from cobalt (III) acetate which he used.

* In the various steps of the reaction, cobalt (III) ion has been denoted by Co^{3+} for brevity. Undoubtedly, a cobalt (III) ion will be associated with the molecules of water and sulphate anion.

With still higher concentrations of acetic acid (3.00 *M* and >), the order of reaction with respect to the organic compound increases from one and may become even two. It may, therefore, be suggested that under these conditions, more than one molecule of acetic acid take part in the formation of the activated complex, which then fragments, giving the reaction products.

The concentrations of amino acetic acid used are low and it has been observed that nature of the reaction is similar to that of acetic acid where its lower concentrations (< 0.125 *M*) have been used. Hence, a similar mechanism can be proposed here also.

In the reaction of cobalt (III) with monochloroacetic acid, traces of chlorine have been detected. It, therefore, appears more reasonable to believe that chlorine replacing one of the hydrogen atoms in the methyl group, comes out as free chlorine and may yield glycollic acid, which in turn can rapidly be oxidised by cobalt (III) to yield carbon dioxide and water. Thus, the kinetic studies of the oxidation of monochloroacetic acid by cobalt (III) are similar to those observed in the case of glycollic acid⁶.

The order of reaction for cobalt (III) is one while reacting with trichloroacetic acid and traces of chlorine are found in the reaction mixture. It has, therefore, to be concluded that the oxidation of this compound is effected in the same manner as has been suggested for the reaction between acetic acid and cobalt (III) containing concentrated solutions of the former (0.125 to 2.00 *M*).

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